

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE: THE NEED OF THE HOUR FOR MITIGATING THE EFFECT OF WORK STRESS ON WORK PERFORMANCE-A COMPREHENSIVE RESEARCH ANALYSIS

ANAMIKA SINGH

Research Scholar, Institute of Management Studies, Banaras Hindu University.
Email: singhanamika.282@gmail.com

Dr. RAJKIRAN PRABHAKAR

Assistant Professor, Institute of Management Studies, Banaras Hindu University.
Email: rajkiranprabhakar@fmsbhu.ac.in

Abstract

The year 1990 saw the initial mention of the term "Emotional Intelligence" (EI) in academic journals. Both the number of studies conducted on EI and the number of models developed in this area have grown dramatically since then. Recently, the idea of "emotional intelligence" (EI) has gained a lot of attraction in the business world. The subject has recently exploded in popularity, affecting even organizational psychologists. This study compiles and synthesizes research on the following topics: the role of emotional intelligence as a moderator between stress at work and performance on the job; how to reduce the negative impact of stress at work on performance on the job; and how to perform well under pressure.

Emotional Intelligence

Intelligence, defined by cognitive abilities like remembering and solving problems, was a concept utilized by ancient Greek philosophers such as Aristotle. Descartes, another philosopher, characterized intelligence as the capacity to distinguish between reality and fabrication. It is possible for a person's IQ to fluctuate depending on the context, according to E. L. Thorndike (1920), who distinguished between mechanical, social, and abstract intelligence in the early 20th century. In the 1920s, Thorndike initially put up the idea of EI as social intelligence. Thorndike stated in the 1930s that social intelligence is the capacity to get along with individuals. These abilities are crucial in practically every facet of life, as per the theories and study of emotional intelligence (EI) (Salovey & Grewal, 2005). Additionally, Thorndike characterized social intelligence as the capacity to comprehend and guide individuals of either sex toward suitable behavior in social contexts (Thorndike, 1920).

Companies in the present day are notoriously unpredictable, full of change, and constantly looking for methods to increase output. It takes more than working in a typical team setting or even working alone to get things done. These days, being able to communicate, connect, empathize, and gain knowledge from coworkers is vital. These days, it takes a lot of intelligence and a high IQ to get a job.

The concept was expanded upon in 1997 from EI to encompass the following abilities: "perceive accurately, appraise, and express emotion; the ability to access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought; the capacity to understand emotion and

emotional knowledge; and the ability to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth" (Mayer & Salovey, 1997).

Work Stress—Analysis of Previous Research and Development

Stress and Causes of Stress

What Selye refers to as anxiety is a "nonspecific response to damage of any kind of stress". He elaborated on the term "stressor" to describe the external factor that set off the body's stress reaction. One can have a good or negative outlook on stress. Positive stress, often known as eustress, is a form of constructive stress that enhances performance in difficult situations. It appears that problems emerge when resources are exhausted, leading to burnout, even if the General Adaptation Syndrome considers eustress as a physiological reaction and early warning signal. Negative stress occurs when we push through physical symptoms of exhaustion and risk burnout. Creating a stress-management program and a positive work environment for employees is becoming more difficult for companies.

Difficulty in Categorizing Stress

One major challenge in developing causal models is the difficulty of stress classification. The word "stress" has distinct meanings in different academic disciplines, claims Hinkle. Social scientists study how stress affects people's feelings and actions, whereas biologists study how organisms and their environments function from the inside out. Different people experience and cope with stress in different ways depending on a wide range of characteristics, including their unique personalities, sense of self-worth, locus of control, coping style, resilience, attribution style, demographics, expectations, preferences, commitment, health-related variables, capacities, and skills. When stressors aren't stressors, people don't "perceive them as such", says Briner et al. (2004).

Emotional intelligence and Stress

For instance, Slaski and Cartwright (2002) delved into the links between EI and health and performance. The researchers hypothesised that EI is a key factor in determining one's mental well-being and life success because it is believed to impact one's ability to deal with external demands and stresses. People who scored higher on the EI scale reported better health, happiness, and performance, in addition to lower stress levels, according to research. There is a strong correlation between EI and both mental and physical health, as pointed out by Dulewics, Higgs, and Slaski (2003). Researchers Mikolajczak et al. (2007) discovered that EI significantly predicts the occurrence of both mental and physical health issues associated with stress. In addition, studies conducted by Slaski and Cartwright suggest that EI can mitigate the effects of stress and even boost resilience (2002). Research out of South Africa that Brand (2007) states looked into the connection between EI, occupational stress, and nurses' health lends credence to this theory. Ciarrochi, Deane, and Anderson (2002) came to similar conclusions: EI mediates the association between stress and many indicators of mental health, including despair, suicidal ideation, and hopelessness. According to these findings, EI is negatively

correlated with stress and health concerns. Those who score higher on the EI scale will also be better equipped to handle the stresses and strains of their everyday lives, according to this research.

Analysis of Research papers on Emotional Intelligence and its impact on Stress

According to Klohnen (1996), implementing Emotional Intelligence into the workplace can lead to numerous advantages, such as a higher stress tolerance, improved people management abilities, and enhanced performance.

Stress and emotional intelligence were the subjects of Abraham's (2000) research. His research led her to the conclusion that EQ correlates negatively with stress levels, positive conflict styles, and other indicators of thriving in challenging work environments.

An Indian version of the Emotional Intelligence test was the subject of study by Thingujam and Ram (2000). Compared to trait-anxiety, which was found to have a negative association with most Emotional Intelligence categories, coping and social relations were found to have a substantial positive link.

Research by Slaski and Cartwright (2002) examined the connections between EQ, subjective stress, health, morale, work-life balance, and managerial effectiveness. There was a random selection of 224 managers from an Irish retail firm. The study found that EQ is positively correlated with aspects including overall health, morale, and quality of working life, and negatively correlated with subjective stress.

A study conducted by Nikolaou, Ioannis; L. Tsaousis (2002) examined the correlation between stress and emotional intelligence in mental health care practitioners. An Emotional Intelligence questionnaire and the Organization Stress Screening Tool were administered to 212 individuals. The study found a negative correlation between emotional intelligence and stress.

A study conducted by Jordan, Ashkanasy, and Hartel (2002) suggests that emotional intelligence plays a role in how people react to job insecurity and how they deal with stress. Specifically, it was found that people with lower emotional intelligence were more likely to have negative reactions to job insecurity and to use negative coping mechanisms compared to those with higher emotional intelligence.

The capacity to cope with stress as well as one's mental and physical well-being were postulated by Gardner and Stough (2003) as potential determinants of EI. Important predictors of professional stress, according to regression research, were emotional control and management. The research presented here supports the idea that employees' capacity to handle their emotions and the information related to their emotions at work contributes to their resilience in the face of stress and to their overall mental health.

Stress, according to Chabungban (2005), may be expensive for businesses and people alike if nobody pays attention to it. Reduce stress and boost productivity with the help of emotional intelligence training. Workers that are emotionally intelligent are better able to manage their own emotions, including anger, annoyance, and frustration, as well as boost their own motivation, self-assurance, empathy, and response times.

A study conducted by Day, Therrien, and Carroll (2005) examined the potential of emotional intelligence to foretell the effects of stress and pressure on health. Daily problems, psychological health, strain factors, and emotional intelligence (as measured by the trait-based EQ-i) were all part of the investigation.

Michailidis M. and Georgiou Y. (2005) studied sixty banking industry workers to determine their degrees of organizational stress. The study's findings demonstrated an inverse relationship between stress and EQ scores. Emotional intelligence (EQ) and its relationship to executives' subjective well-being and locus of control was studied by Kulshrestha et al. (2006) in India. The study's sample consisted of 150 executives from various levels of the automotive industry's professional hierarchy. Subjective well-being is significantly correlated with emotional intelligence and locus of control, according to the study's results.

The impact of emotional intelligence on the expected state of mental health was investigated by Shulman and Hemenover (2006). Emotional distress, psychological health, and understanding and regulation of emotions were among the assessments that the participants filled out. The second round of scales was filled out. Both the cross-sectional relationship and the predictive power of dispositional emotional intelligence were found to be associated with health outcomes.

An analysis of 312 medical professionals (174 men and 138 female doctors) was carried out by Singh & Singh (2008) to determine the effect of Emotional Intelligence on the perception of Role Stress. There was no statistically significant difference in the levels of emotional intelligence or perceived role stress between the sexes, however there was a negative correlation between EQ and organizational role stress for both male and female medical professionals.

Stress can be seen as both an input and an output of emotional intelligence (or its lack), according to research by Ramesar, Koortzen, and Oosthuizen (2009). Emotional intelligence includes the capacity to regulate and cope with stress.

A study conducted by Saddam Hussain Rahim (2010) examined banking sector employees. The sample was drawn at random from 23 different banks, with 3 being public sector banks, 18 being private sector banks, and 2 being foreign banks. Although each bank had more than 3000 employees, data was collected from 630 employees according to the requirements of the study. The results demonstrate that EI competencies significantly affect stress levels, and they draw the conclusion that managers with high EI are able to regulate their employees' stress levels.

Stress and emotional intelligence were the subjects of research by Chhabra and Mohanty (2013), who looked at three tiers of management. The sample included 103 managers from different private sector organizations, distributed across three tiers of management: senior, middle, and junior. Among the three tiers of management, EI and job stress varied significantly according to the analysis of variance results; the most senior managers outperformed their less experienced colleagues on the EI test. But compared to the other two tiers, senior managers reported lower levels of stress. Because EI accounted for 24%

of the variance in work stress, regression analysis demonstrated that EI has a substantial influence on stress management at work.

Based on the work of Dilip Singh, Gangai and Agrawal (2013) investigated the function of emotional intelligence (EI) in stress management in the workplace. The results indicate that stress has a negative correlation with emotional intelligence and that stress levels can be used to predict emotional intelligence, which is partially confirmed.

Among the second-year M.B.B.S. students at the Post Graduate Institute of Medical Sciences in Rohtak, researchers Malik, Chaudhary, and Kumari (2017) found that people who are emotionally intelligent tend to be less stressed.

Research by Agila and Padmanabhan (2017) sought to answer the question, "How is emotional intelligence related to organizational stress?" by surveying workers at Prudential Assurance Malaysia Berhad. The results demonstrated a strong correlation between EQ and stress in the workplace. According to the study's findings, companies should give EI training to their staff in order to alleviate stress in the workplace.

Das, Deepa, and Venkateshwaran (2019) surveyed 371 insurance workers and documented their opinions. By teaching workers effective coping mechanisms, researchers were able to raise EI levels and alleviate or redirect stress on the job from the get-go.

The purpose of the study by Bhatt and Sharma (2020) was to examine the relationship between emotional intelligence and stress levels among college students attending professional institutes in Dehradun, Uttarakhand, India. This study's results demonstrated an inverse relationship between EI and COVID-19 stress, but no such relationship with perceived stress. While EI might not be a reliable predictor of how you'll react to chronic stress in general, our research suggests it could help you cope with extreme stressors like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Using Goleman's Theory of Emotional Intelligence, Fteiha & Awwad (2020) studied 265 students to determine their EQ and how they cope with stress. Emotional intelligence was found to be positively correlated with both active and passive issue coping strategies. Furthermore, it was shown that emotional intelligence was inversely related to passive emotional coping and passive issue coping.

Sources of work stress

1. Job Satisfaction

An individual's sentiments, beliefs, and emotional investment in their work are the components that make up their job attitude. There are two ways to think about attitude toward work in general. employment satisfaction can be defined in two ways: first, as an emotional state that encompasses a wide range of subjective experiences with one's employment; and second, as an aggregate of objective cognitive evaluations of various elements of one's job, including but not limited to compensation, working conditions, opportunities, and more. Workers assess their career progression prospects by closely observing their job, profession, and employer. How a person feels, thinks, and acts while

on the job is known as their "work attitude" (Carmeli, 2003). The ability of one's employment to meet one's physical and psychological demands is one component of the multi-faceted emotional response known as "job satisfaction" (Carmeli 2003). It is common practice to use job satisfaction as a surrogate measure of how happy an individual is in their job.

"Complex emotional reactions to the job" are what Locke called "work satisfaction" and "work dissatisfaction" (Locke, 1969). There is a positive correlation between emotional intelligence and job happiness, according to a conceptualization of job satisfaction as "feeling or affective responses to facets of the situation" (Smith et al., 1969). Furthermore, it is commonly believed that an employee's level of job satisfaction is indicative of their overall well-being on the job (Grandey, 2000).

(As a result of stress in teachers), Gardner (2005) proved that occupational stressor exposure correlates with levels of job satisfaction. To that end, this section provides a concise overview of the study's focus on work satisfaction, the primary outcome of occupational stress.

2. Role overload

According to this metric, organizational constraints are causing employees to be overworked. Employees feel pressured in situations like this.

According to Eatough et al. (2011), role overload occurs when an individual feels that their own resources are not enough to handle the demands of their job. Even while role stress and the experiences it brings are unavoidable, it can have a negative impact on an organization's ability to perform when members are under excessive stress. Competent management of perceived role stress is essential for the efficient performance of any work with several responsibilities. Both researchers and working professionals tend to agree that stress levels should be kept at a minimum in order to avoid the unpleasant emotions that can result from being under too much pressure.

3. Role Ambiguity

In particular, when the expected actions of an employee are not clear or even contradictory, we say that their roles are ambiguous or conflicting (Rizzo et al., 1970).

From the standpoint of role theory, which states that employees are structured to carry out necessary roles (i.e., interdependent, recurring behaviors; Katz and Kahn, 1978) for the organization's survival, the trio of role stressors—i.e., role overload, role ambiguity, and role conflict—has arisen as a prominent typology among the numerous work stressors that have been studied. Role stresses are those that arise from the repetitive interactions between people in various roles and responsibilities.

When employees are unsure about their specific roles, it can lead to stress. Some examples of this include having to complete a large amount of work in a short amount of time, dealing with conflicting demands from guests and the organization, and having supervisors that try to discourage democratic practices in the department.

This aspect shows that employees experience stress due to role ambiguity. Employees are put through a lot of stress when they aren't clear about the goals of their assignments or when they don't know what kind of behavior or performance their superiors and peers expect from them.

4. Physical Distress or Role Inadequacy

According to Eatough et al. (2011), role overload occurs when an individual feels that their own resources are not enough to handle the demands of their job. People experience stress in response to real or perceived losses of resources; this includes both existing and future resources (Hobfoll, 1989, 2001). Negative emotions and fatigue are common responses to real or perceived resource depletion (Crawford et al., 2010; Halbesleben et al., 2014). Therefore, the severity of resource loss and strain (e.g., ranging from general felt strain to depression) is directly proportional to the degree to which there is an imbalance between the demands of the position and the resources available to fulfill it.

5. Dealing with Change

The way stress assessment mediates the relationship between employees' perceptions of transformational change and their in-role performance is important to consider. Various people, according to cognitive appraisal theory, have various ways of evaluating the same kinds of stressors, such as challenges and obstacles. Transformative change is a significant stressor that, according to people's evaluations, impacts them in different ways.

An enormous danger to human health and property, the COVID-19 pandemic has caused worldwide economic upheavals never seen before (Chakraborty and Maity, 2020). Both opportunities and threats are presented by this abrupt shift (Kovoor-Misra, 2009). As a result, most businesses adapt to new circumstances by making little but steady adjustments that boost their long-term competitiveness and propel them forward (Brown and Eisenhardt, 1997; May and Stahl, 2017).

6. Self -Esteem

A person's organization based self-esteem is a reflection of how much they value and are acknowledged as a productive and competent individual in the workplace. It is the value that an employee feels about himself as a result of his involvement in the organization. A high degree of self-esteem is associated with a perception of an employee's abilities, significance, competence, and value to the company (Pierce et al., 1989; Pierce and Gardner, 2004; Kim and Beehr, 2018; Neves et al., 2020; Rice et al., 2020).

Factors including individual self-esteem, work experiences, and organizational ideals and structure all play a role in determining the degree of organization-based self-esteem. Brookover et al. (1964), Korman (1970), Brockner (1988), Baumeister (1999), McAllister and Bigley (2002), Pierce and Gardner (2004), Kim and Beehr (2018), and others have found that social interactions, the social learning experience, and the messages received and internalized from important others all play a role in shaping self-esteem in the workplace.

7. Work environment

According to the various study's findings, lower-level employees experience a negative work environment due to factors such as gender discrimination, unsatisfactory working conditions from a welfare perspective, a large workload, lack of clarity regarding future career prospects within the current organization, a lack of variety in tasks, poor communication with coworkers, and the inability to resolve conflicts arising from competing demands.

8. Work -Life Balance

There are various ways in which one's standard of living can be improved through work, which is an integral aspect of our lives. Each person at each stage of life views work-life balance in their own unique way (Kumar.K & Chaturvedi.R, 2017). Having some say over one's work schedule, location, and methods is key to achieving a healthy work-life balance. It is attained when everyone's right to live a life they love, both at work and outside of it, is recognized and valued as the standard, for the benefit of everyone involved (Uddin et al, 2013).

Maintaining a healthy work-life balance impacts one's financial, social, spiritual, and physical health. It influences a person's character in every way: their outlook, values, actions, perception, emotions, and personality traits. Ever since the concept of work-life balance was first proposed in 1986, it has been an ongoing struggle for employees to find a happy medium between their professional and personal lives. Byrne (2005) and Rife and Hall (2015) found that employees who had achieved work-life balance reported less conflict and more fulfillment in their personal and professional lives. Policymakers, organizations, managers, employees, and their representatives around the world are all paying attention to the importance of work-life balance as a field of human resource management (McCarthy, Darcy & Grady, 2010).

Work Performance

Work performance, which is influenced by many things including job stress, can be defined as the degree to which an individual is able to complete a task within the usual limitations of making reasonable use of the resources at his or her disposal.

A person's performance is the end outcome of their efforts to reach a target according to a predetermined metric. Reasoning, problem-solving, decision-making, and any other form of non-observable mental processing could fall under this category (Bailey and Robert, 2003). According to research by Brown et al. (1997), emotions are potent psychological actions that have a significant impact on behavior and performance. In what ways do the various EI competencies impact productivity in the workplace? Improving employee performance should be the first order of business for many companies seeking to increase performance and carry out economic activities as efficiently as possible.

A person's performance is influenced by their level of knowledge, abilities, motivations, and skills. In today's fast-paced business world, where employee behaviors and

motivations are always evolving, emotional intelligence is a crucial competency. Although studies have demonstrated a strong correlation between EQ and productivity on the job.

Emotional Intelligence and Work Performance

Since controlling one's emotions is an essential part of managing one's social behavior (Hochschild, 1983), EI may serve as a reliable indicator of success. Organizations can benefit from a legitimate alternative to traditional methods of hiring and performance evaluation when they connect EI with performance. Emotions in the workplace have lately been the subject of increased attention from organizational researchers. As an example, Ashforth and Humphrey (1993) state that employees' emotional experiences should be given more attention because emotions are an essential and inseparable component of organizational life. Many organizational behaviorists have sought to identify factors that impact employees' performance at work in response to the growing importance of emotional intelligence, which has been cited as a crucial contributor to organizational success (Goleman, 1998; Salovey and Mayor, 1990; Weinberger, 2002). Researchers in the fields of emotional labor and emotion management have shown that managers' actions and even seemingly little changes to the company's environment can have a significant effect on workers' emotional reactions and, by extension, their productivity (Hochschild, 1983; Huy, 1999). Therefore, managers can enhance employee performance by gaining insight into the impact of emotions on mental processes and actions.

According to Borman & Motowidlo (1993), job performance consists of two main factors:

- **Task performance-** It lays out the fundamental duties that every worker must perform on the job. This type of conduct, which is also known as "in-role prescribed behavior," is evident in the number and quality of certain work results and deliverables.
- **Contextual performance-** It extends beyond the bounds of a typical workday. Often called "discretionary extra-role behavior," contextual performance manifests itself in things like mentoring colleagues, building organizational social networks, and exceeding expectations.

Individual Work Performance

The idea of individual work performance emerged as new criteria were incorporated over time. Task performance, contextual performance, adaptive performance, and counterproductive work behavior are the four theoretical elements that make up individual work performance (IWP).

Any "behaviors or actions that are relevant to the goals of the organization" are generally considered IWP. Employee behaviors or activities, rather than the outcomes of these actions, are used to define IWP. Also, IWP doesn't include actions that are limited by external factors because it only includes behaviors that the person can influence. The four generic and overarching dimensions of IWP were recently suggested in a multi-disciplinary systematic literature review as part of a heuristic framework.

According to Koopmans et al. (2011), the heuristic framework for evaluating individual performance on the job includes four dimensions: task performance, contextual performance, adaptive performance, and counterproductive work behavior.

Task Performance: The first measure is task performance, which is how well an employee does their main job duties.

When it comes to the second factor, contextual performance, it's about how employees act in ways that support the work, social, and mental setting where the main tasks are carried out.

The third dimension is Adaptive performance which is how well an employee can adjust to changes in their job or the place where they work.

The fourth dimension is counterproductive work behavior, which is behavior that hurts the company.

Employee Work Performance -Review of Literature of its relationship with Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman's (1998) research, people can actually develop their EI competencies over time. Emotional intelligence can also be cultivated in adults through training.

The average objective achievement of the most successful debt collectors at a big collection agency during a three-month period was studied by Bachman et al. (2000). Another set of collectors whose mean was substantially lower was used for the comparison. The results demonstrated that the department's top collectors exhibited much greater levels of the Emotional Intelligence competences of optimism, self-awareness, and independence.

According to a number of longitudinal studies done by Boyatziz (2002), people's EI competencies change over the course of two to five years. One third of the variation in performance levels was explained by technical skills and cognitive capacity, while the other two thirds was explained by emotional competence, according to a sample of 200 organizations' personnel.

A person's emotional intelligence (EQ) is crucial to their success, according to research by Bhalla, S., and Nauriyal, D. K. (2004). EQ may also help us understand and forecast how well people will do on the job.

While some have argued that EI does not significantly impact work performance, the majority of studies have shown a favorable correlation between the two (Slaski & Cartwright, 2003; Bar-On, 2005).

Emotional intelligence, performance, and stress were the subjects of Chabungban's (2005) research. The results of his study demonstrated that improving one's emotional intelligence can help with both stress management and productivity.

The importance of EI in organizations has been extensively discussed in literature on performance. According to Kunnanatt (2008), his research proved that EI is helpful in raising both individual and company output

Researchers Chiva and Alegre (2008) looked examined how EQ relates to contentment on the work. The results demonstrated a robust relationship between Emotional Intelligence and job happiness, which in turn was associated with improved performance.

Over the last many decades, people have debated and disputed over the distinctions between intellect and emotion. Some results run counter to the initial conclusions that IQ is not a reliable indicator of future success or productivity on the job (Manley, 2009).

Using a four-factor model of cultural intelligence, Moon (2010) investigated the connections between EQ and CI. Results showed a correlation between emotional and cultural quotient and a range of skills, including the ability to manage one's own emotions and behaviors, as well as competence in dealing with others from different cultural backgrounds. It follows that those high in emotional intelligence should have little trouble adjusting to new cultures.

In a global survey of professionals, Boyatzis et al. (2010) found that a high level of emotional and social intelligence was significantly associated with better job performance and effectiveness. The study emphasized that a manager's emotional intelligence is crucial for reading people's emotions and leading them effectively

Researchers Dhani, Sehrawat, and Sharma (2016) set out to determine whether there is a correlation between Emotional Intelligence (EI) and work performance in Indian companies' middle management.

A study was carried out by Radha& Shree (2017) on a group of one hundred software industry middle-level personnel. Emotional intelligence is a key component that impacts employee performance, according to this study.

In their study, Brodya, Gupta, and Salter (2020) recruited undergraduates majoring in accounting and master's degree candidates in business administration from Australia who had previously taken the Genos International Emotional Intelligence Inventory.

According to the regression results of the study by Mathushan and Nanthagopan (2020), emotional intelligence accounts for 48.8% of an employee's performance.

Review of Related Literature on Performance and Stress

There has been a lack of consistency in the research on the link between stress at work and productivity on the job. Some empirical research have discovered positive linear or U-linked associations between stress and performance, however most of them have showed a negative linear relationship (Siu, 2003; Van Dyne, Jehn, & Cumming, 2005).

Moreover, research by Montgomery, Blodgett, and Barnes (1996) has shown that work stress can significantly affect an individual's life and career within the organization. This is due to the fact that stress plays a role in both lowering motivation and job performance and increasing motivation to work. Exchange rate for jobs.

According to Siu (2003), when people cope with stress, it lowers their concentration and energy levels on a certain activity, which in turn severely affects their work performance.

Work stress is associated with a number of negative outcomes, including but not limited to decreased productivity, higher employee turnover, decreased organizational satisfaction, decreased motivation, and tardiness (Glazer and Beehr, 2005). Workers' decision-making abilities can be further compromised by stress at work.

Pflanz and Ogle (2006) also discovered that 800 Air Force personnel in Wyoming, USA, were less productive, had trouble finishing tasks within a certain time frame, and were more likely to miss work due to stress. Workplace accidents are on the rise, and it's a big reason why.

In line with earlier research (Gilboa et al., 2008; Siu, 2003; Van Dyne et al., 2002), Wu (2011) discovered that job performance is negatively correlated with work stress.

In a related study, Suandi, Ismail, and Othman (2014) surveyed 168 employees from the Northern Department of Education in Perlis, Kedah, and Penang, and they discovered that even moderate to normal levels of stress may guarantee good to excellent performance. The pattern is different for low stress levels.

Further, a study examining 60 government officials in North Sulawesi, Indonesia, discovered that job performance is significantly affected by work stress, with a particular emphasis on workload and surroundings. This research was carried out by Roring, Soegoto, and Dotulong (2014).

Consequently, employees lack the will to take initiative and come up with new ideas at work. Employee conduct is impacted by stress levels in the workplace.

Emotional intelligence moderating the relationship between Work Stress and Work Performance

King and Gardner (2006) discovered that people with high emotional intelligence were better able to comprehend emotional states through cognitive evaluations, and that the most effective strategies for dealing with stressful work environments included utilizing social resources and expressing professional feelings. They further claim that resilience and flexibility are traits associated with emotionally intelligent people.

According to Wu's (2011) research, EQ can moderate the connection between stress on the workplace and productivity. According to him, stress might originate from where the pressure is applied, but it can also impact how an individual perceives the situation. Workplace stress can have a negative impact on performance, but employees with high or poor emotional intelligence are more equipped to deal with this issue than those with low EQ, according to his research. This study's findings also show that those who aren't very emotionally intelligent struggle to handle pressure on the job.

Furthermore, Yozgat, Yurtkoru, and Bolginoglu (2013) studied 424 public sector workers in Istanbul and discovered that in spite of a stressful work environment, people with high emotional intelligence were able to maintain company-standard performance.

Sharma, Dhar, and Tyagi (2015) examined 693 nursing staff members in Uttarakhand, India, and found that EQ predicts performance, can influence workplace conflict, and allows nurses to control their mental health.

When workers are unable to adjust to their working conditions, it can lead to stress on the job. Emotional intelligence, on the other hand, can serve as a moderating factor and help an employee succeed. In their 2016 study, Sony and Mekoth examined 517 electric utility operator professionals in India. The researchers looked at how emotional intelligence predicted variables including job satisfaction, performance, and adaptability on the job.

Researchers Rezvani and Khosravi (2019) also discovered that employees with high levels of emotional intelligence were better able to manage stress at work, which in turn led to higher levels of productivity and performance. The study surveyed 363 software developers from Australia. When people are able to build healthy, competitive relationships at work, it's even more valuable.

Actually, it's the individual's perception of stress, not the source of stress, that causes it. So, in this study, people with high levels of emotional intelligence were able to mitigate the negative effects of workplace stress on their performance or at least keep them to a respectable level, whereas those with lower levels of emotional intelligence were unable to do so. Employees who lack emotional intelligence are less capable of handling pressure well and acting professionally in all scenarios.

Internal variables also have a role in adding to the external elements that contribute to work strain. Consequently, everyone is subject to a different amount of pressure depending on how much they feel it affects them.

Emotional Intelligence at the workplace

Having high levels of emotional intelligence can help in many different areas of life. The professional environment, however, is where its usefulness has been most extensively documented. Workplaces provide a consistent environment for evaluating and developing emotional intelligence skills, according to Cherniss and Goleman (1993):

- 1) The ability to manage one's emotions is fundamental to success in a wide variety of fields.
- 2) Many adults join the workforce unprepared to meet or surpass their employers' expectations in their roles.
- 3) Companies already have the infrastructure and motivation to provide emotional intelligence training.
- 4) The majority of working-age adults devote the majority of their waking hours to their jobs.

Nunnally and Bernstein (2020) state that companies' understanding of emotional concepts demonstrates a strong eagerness for the expert utilizations of Emotional Intelligence. Leadership, an essential trait in the workplace, has been the focus of much research on emotional intelligence.

According to Ko Seon Hee (2021), one way to boost customer service is to focus more on psychological compensation, which manifests as listening attentively and demonstrating empathy (a component of EI). In order to keep a positive work atmosphere, it is necessary to control negative emotions like anger, which are a component of emotional intelligence (EI), and the many subcategories of angry feeling can make their detection difficult.

Cherniss found that leaders who were able to establish mutual respect, trust, and a special glow and connection with their followers fared better. Given that many studies have argued that a leader's ability to handle the unexpected social challenges that can arise in companies is fundamental to compelling leadership, this finding should not be surprising.

Emotional intelligence allows people to attach themselves to or disassociate from emotions in response to certain situations, based on how useful those emotions are at that moment. One way this manifests itself is when the person is able to rein in their impulses, delay making a snap decision, and then express their thoughts with poise and consideration. Practices like "pause, breathe, and relax then respond," "count to ten before replying," and the advice to "think and then act" are all attempts at emotional regulation through appropriate communication of sentiments and emotions. It is common practice to instruct even the youngest children to "smile for Grandpa" or "count to 10" before becoming angry. One strong indicator of emotional regulation competence is the ability to delay instantaneous responses (Zhou, George, 2003).

A person's level of emotional investment in their job and the range of emotions it evokes in them, including happiness, sadness, surprise, and frustration, are additional factors that motivate them beyond the rational exchange approach (Ashforth&Humphrey, 1995, cited in Carmeli, 2003). To thrive in an organization, emotional intelligence is a must. Cognitive abilities "get you in door" of a company, but emotional intelligence impacts everything you do at work, therefore according to Goleman (1998), emotional intelligence helps you succeed once you're hired.

Improving your interactions in social and professional contexts, as well as your personal efficacy, can be achieved through developing your emotional intelligence. Their ability to control their own emotions, as well as those of others, allows them to speak clearly and persuasively, and they have a good impact on others around them. Empowering individuals to perform, develop teamwork, and promote loyalty and retention in the workplace is another benefit. It also helps with increasing flexibility and effectively dealing with change, growth, and conflict.

Emotional Intelligence and Workplace Outcomes

The benefits of emotional intelligence in relation to job-related outcomes, including performance, dedication, and other behaviors related to work, have been the focus of research on the topic.

Research by Boyatzis (1982) on 100 managers from 12 different companies found that Emotional Intelligence, a "self-assessment" skill, was associated with better performance

A study of 450 Massachusetts boys' life outcomes was undertaken by Snarey and Vaillant (1985) to determine the impact of intelligent emotional display. The research spanned four decades. Of the youngsters who took part, two-thirds came from welfare families. This group's IQ was below 90 for one-third of the total. According to the findings, EQ is more relevant to one's capacity to manage their own emotions and frustrations as well as their capacity to build relationships with others than it is to one's actual achievement in life events.

A total of 300 C-suite executives from fifteen different international companies were the subjects of research by Spencer, Jr., and Spencer (1993). Emotional abilities including influence, team leadership, organizational awareness, self-confidence, accomplishment desire, and leadership were found to be a significant differentiator between average and top performance in the study.

Research by Goldman on the professional paths taken by Harvard Business School alums was examined by Stauffer (1997). According to Goleman's research, graduates with a higher emotional quotient (EQ) had better job prospects than those with a higher IQ.

According to Goleman's (1998) research, people can actually develop their EI competencies over time. Emotional intelligence can also be cultivated in adults through training.

The correlation between emotional intelligence and chronological age has been the subject of several studies. Age and experience were found to have a favorable and statistically significant relationship with emotional intelligence.

Using a case study approach, Cherniss et al. (2001) investigated why financial advisors at American Express (US) failed to incorporate life insurance policies into their clients' financial plans. When tested on measures of emotional intelligence, the majority of agents scored below average. According to the research, it would be beneficial to create programs that focus on emotional competence and ensure that programmers possess the appropriate level of emotional competence for optimal performance. A striking upward trend in policy sales was seen following a two and a half year successful implementation.

An individual's level of emotional intelligence is a strong predictor of their success in life and their ability to succeed in the workplace, according to research by Bhalla and Nauriyal (2004).

In a study of New Zealand employees, Cummings (2005) looked at how EQ correlated with demographics and productivity on the job. According to his findings, there is a strong correlation between EQ and success on the job, but no correlation between EQ and other demographic variables like age, gender, occupation, or level of education.

Emotional intelligence, performance, and stress were the subjects of Chabungban's (2005) research. A decrease in stress and an increase in performance can be achieved

through the cultivation of emotional intelligence, according to his research. The findings were corroborated by (Singh & Singh, 2008) looked at the yearly KRA performance scores of 240 managers in India's manufacturing sector and discovered that EQ helped with stress management and was a good predictor of good scores.

While discussing the dynamics of intergroup conflict and the stress it causes in groups, Hede (2006) made an effort to present the idea of a made-up shadow group. He arrived to the conclusion that the overt and shadow selves are the two primary polar opposites that make up a person's natural self. Everyone in the group acts in accordance with the group's shadow members when they feel emotionally threatened, because the shadow self-engulfs the overt self. He stated that emotionally intelligent people understand the dynamic between the overt and the covert and can stay in the covert to avoid negative outcomes.

Companies actively seek out candidates with high levels of emotional intelligence, according to research. Organizations are encouraged to make Emotional Intelligence a part of their everyday operations by providing training in the skill, modifying their placement and selection procedures, providing counseling, and promoting positive behaviors through their performance evaluation and compensation system.

Researchers Chiva and Alegre (2008) looked examined how EQ relates to contentment on the work. A high level of emotional intelligence was associated with a happy workplace, and a happy workplace was associated with better performance.

Results from a study by Khokhar and Kush (2009) on the relationship between emotional intelligence (EQ) and work performance were consistent with these findings. The study found that executives with higher degrees of emotional intelligence also performed better.

Moon (2010) explored the implications of EQ and CI using a four-factor model of cultural intelligence. The findings indicate a connection between emotional and cultural quotient and many abilities, such as cross-cultural communication skills, self-awareness, independence, and competency. So, it was concluded that those who are emotionally intelligent would find it simpler to adapt to other cultures.

Cheung and Tang (2010) investigated a sample of academic leaders to learn more about the connection between EQ and transformative leadership, with the goal of elucidating the ways in which cultural variations impact leadership and academic practices. When looking at cross-cultural leadership practices, the results showed a positive correlation with emotional intelligence competencies.

High levels of emotional and social intelligence were substantially linked to higher job performance and effectiveness, according to a worldwide study of professionals conducted by Boyatzis et al. (2010). Managers require a high degree of emotional intelligence, which enables them to perceive people's signs, for successful communication and leadership.

In their study, Crowne et al. (2013) discovered a link between social intelligence (SI), emotional intelligence (EI), and cultural intelligence (CQ). Online questionnaires were

taken by 467 American students enrolled in business courses. The investigations were carried out using Principal Component Analysis and Structural Equation Modeling. Using AMOS, we constructed many models of the interplay of social, emotional, and cultural intelligences in order to test the null hypothesis that social intelligence is more significant than the three separately defined qualities. The results show that CI and EQ are two aspects of personality that are distinct from one another but related. The development of multiple independent models to support the various assertions was the first step in the long process that culminated in the final integrated model.

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